

Locally closed sets and g -locally closed sets in binary topological spaces

O. Nethaji^{1*} and R. Premkumar²

¹PG and Research Department of Mathematics, Kamaraj College,
Thoothukudi-628 003, Tamil Nadu, India. ORCID iD: [0000-0002-2004-3521](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2004-3521)

²Department of Mathematics, Arul Anandar College, Karumathur,
Madurai-625 514, Tamil Nadu, India. ORCID iD: [0000-0002-8088-5114](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8088-5114)

Received: 03 May 2023

Accepted: 19 Jul 2023

Published Online: 31 Aug 2023

Abstract: In this paper, we focused on locally closed sets in binary topological spaces and certain properties of these investigated. Also, we studied the binary generalized locally closed sets, binary g - lc^* , binary g - lc^{**} and established their various characteristic properties.

Key words: binary locally closed sets, binary g -lc, binary g - lc^* , binary g - lc^{**}

1. Introduction and Preliminaries

In 2011, S.Nithyanantha Jothi and P.Thangavelu [8] introduced topology between two sets and also studied some of their properties. Topology between two sets is the binary structure from X to Y which is defined to be the ordered pairs (A, B) where $A \subseteq X$ and $B \subseteq Y$. Recently some researcher developed some new kind of modern topologies for example ([12], [13], and [1]). In this paper, we focused on locally closed sets in binary topological spaces and certain properties of these investigated. Also, we studied the binary generalized locally closed sets, binary g - lc^* , binary g - lc^{**} and established their various characteristic properties.

We denote the boundary of (A, B) by $bd(A, B)$.

Let X and Y be any two nonempty sets. A binary topology [8] from X to Y is a binary structure $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \mathbb{P}(X) \times \mathbb{P}(Y)$ that satisfies the axioms namely

1. (ϕ, ϕ) and $(X, Y) \in \mathcal{M}$,
2. $(A_1 \cap A_2, B_1 \cap B_2) \in \mathcal{M}$ whenever $(A_1, B_1) \in \mathcal{M}$ and $(A_2, B_2) \in \mathcal{M}$, and
3. If $\{(A_\alpha, B_\alpha) : \alpha \in \delta\}$ is a family of members of \mathcal{M} , then $(\bigcup_{\alpha \in \delta} A_\alpha, \bigcup_{\alpha \in \delta} B_\alpha) \in \mathcal{M}$.

If \mathcal{M} is a binary topology from X to Y then the triplet (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) is called a binary topological space and the members of \mathcal{M} are called the binary open subsets of the binary topological space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) . The elements of $X \times Y$ are called the binary points of the binary topological space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) . If $Y = X$ then \mathcal{M} is called a binary topology on X in which case we write (X, \mathcal{M}) as a binary topological space.

Definition 1.1. [8] Let X and Y be any two nonempty sets and let (A, B) and $(C, D) \in \mathbb{P}(X) \times \mathbb{P}(Y)$. We say that $(A, B) \subseteq (C, D)$ if $A \subseteq C$ and $B \subseteq D$.

Definition 1.2. [8] Let (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) be a binary topological space and $A \subseteq X, B \subseteq Y$. Then (A, B) is called binary closed in (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) if $(X \setminus A, Y \setminus B) \in \mathcal{M}$.

Proposition 1.1. [8] Let (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) be a binary topological space and $(A, B) \subseteq (X, Y)$. Let $(A, B)^{1*} = \cap\{A_\alpha : (A_\alpha, B_\alpha) \text{ is binary closed and } (A, B) \subseteq (A_\alpha, B_\alpha)\}$ and $(A, B)^{2*} = \cap\{B_\alpha : (A_\alpha, B_\alpha) \text{ is binary closed and } (A, B) \subseteq (A_\alpha, B_\alpha)\}$. Then $((A, B)^{1*}, (A, B)^{2*})$ is binary closed and $(A, B) \subseteq ((A, B)^{1*}, (A, B)^{2*})$.

Proposition 1.2. [8] Let (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) be a binary topological space and $(A, B) \subseteq (X, Y)$. Let $(A, B)^{1*} = \cup\{A_\alpha : (A_\alpha, B_\alpha) \text{ is binary open and } (A_\alpha, B_\alpha) \subseteq (A, B)\}$ and $(A, B)^{2*} = \cup\{B_\alpha : (A_\alpha, B_\alpha) \text{ is binary open and } (A_\alpha, B_\alpha) \subseteq (A, B)\}$.

Definition 1.3. [8] The ordered pair $((A, B)^{1*}, (A, B)^{2*})$ is called the binary closure of (A, B) , denoted by $b-cl(A, B)$ in the binary space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) where $(A, B) \subseteq (X, Y)$.

Definition 1.4. [8] The ordered pair $((A, B)^{1*}, (A, B)^{2*})$ defined in proposition 1.2 is called the binary interior of (A, B) , denoted by $b-int(A, B)$. Here $((A, B)^{1*}, (A, B)^{2*})$ is binary open and $((A, B)^{1*}, (A, B)^{2*}) \subseteq (A, B)$.

Definition 1.5. [10] A subset (A, B) of a binary topological space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) is called a binary semi open set if $(A, B) \subseteq b-cl(b-int(A, B))$.

Definition 1.6. [9] A subset (A, B) of a binary topological space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) is called a binary g -closed set if $b-cl(A, B) \subseteq (U, V)$ whenever $(A, B) \subseteq (U, V)$ and (U, V) is binary open.

2. Binary Locally Closed Sets

Definition 2.1. A subset (A, B) of a binary topological space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) is called binary locally closed if $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap (G, H)$ where (E, F) is binary open and (G, H) is binary closed in (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) .

The set of all binary locally closed sets of (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) is denoted by $BLC(X, Y)$.

Proposition 2.1. Let (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) be a binary T_1 -space and let (A, B) be a discrete subset of (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) . Then (A, B) is binary locally closed.

2. Let (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) be binary dense-in-itself and (A, B) be a discrete subset. Then $(X, Y) - (A, B)$ is binary locally closed if and only if (A, B) is binary closed.

Proof. Let (A, B) be a discrete subset of the binary T_1 -space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) , i.e. for each $(i, j) \in (A, B)$ there is an binary open set $(E, F)_{(X, Y)}$ such that $(E, F)_{(X, Y)} \cap (A, B) = \{(i, j)\}$. If $(E, F) = \{(E, F)_{(X, Y)} | (i, j) \in (A, B)\}$ then it is easily verified that $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap b-cl(A, B)$. This proves (1).

In order to prove (2), observe that in a binary dense-in-itself space any discrete subset has empty interior.

Proposition 2.2. Let (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) be a space and let $(U, V) \in BLC(X, Y)$. If $(A, B) \in (U, V)$ and $(A, B) \in BLC((U, V), \mathcal{M}/(U, V))$ then $(A, B) \in BLC(X, Y)$.

Proposition 2.3. Let (A, B) and (C, D) be binary locally closed subsets of a space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) . If (A, B) and (C, D) are separated, i.e. if $(A, B) \cap b-cl(C, D) = b-cl((A, B) \cap (C, D)) = (\phi, \phi)$, then $(A, B) \cup (C, D) \in BLC(X, Y)$.

Proof. Suppose there are binary open sets (P, Q) and (S, T) such that $(A, B) = (P, Q) \cap b-cl(A, B)$ and $(C, D) = (S, T) \cap b-cl(C, D)$. Since (A, B) and (C, D) are separated we may assume that $(P, Q) \cap b-cl(C, D) = (S, T) \cap b-cl(A, B) = (\phi, \phi)$. Consequently $(A, B) \cup (C, D) = ((P, Q) \cup (S, T)) \cap b-cl((A, B) \cup (C, D))$ showing that $(A, B) \cup (C, D) \in BLC(X, Y)$.

Theorem 2.1. *Let $\{(U, V)_i | i \in I\}$ be either an binary open cover or a binary locally finite closed cover of a space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) and let $(A, B) \subseteq (X, Y)$. If $(A, B) \cap (U, V)_i \in BLC((U, V)_i, \mathcal{M}/(U, V)_i)$ for each $i \in I$ then $(A, B) \in BLC(X, Y)$.*

Proof. First suppose that $\{(U, V)_i | i \in I\}$ is an binary open cover of (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) . For each $i \in I$, since $(A, B) \cap (U, V)_i \in BLC((U, V)_i, \mathcal{M}/(U, V)_i)$ we may assume that $(A, B) \cap (U, V)_i = (S, T)_i \cap b-cl((A, B) \cap (U, V)_i)$ where $(S, T)_i \in \mathcal{M}$ and $(S, T)_i \subseteq (U, V)_i$. Now $(S, T)_i \cap b-cl(A, B) = (S, T)_i \cap (U, V)_i \cap b-cl(A, B) \subseteq (S, T)_i \cap b-cl((A, B) \cap (U, V)_i) = (A, B) \cap (U, V)_i$. Hence if $(S, T) = \bigcup \{(S, T)_i | i \in I\}$ we have $(S, T) \cap b-cl(A, B) = (A, B)$.

Now suppose that $\{(U, V)_i | i \in I\}$ is a binary locally finite closed cover of (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) . For each $i \in I$, since $(A, B) \cap (U, V)_i \in BLC((U, V)_i, \mathcal{M}/(U, V)_i)$ we have $(A, B) \cap (U, V)_i = (S, T)_i \cap b-cl((A, B) \cap (U, V)_i)$ where $(S, T)_i \in \mathcal{M}$. Let $(x, y) \in (A, B)$. Since $\{(U, V)_i | i \in I\}$ is a binary locally finite closed cover, hence a point-finite and closure-preserving cover, there is a finite subset $I_{(X, Y)} \subseteq I$ such that $(x, y) \in (U, V)_i$ if $I \in I_{(X, Y)}$ and $(x, y) \notin \bigcup \{(U, V)_i | i \in I - I_{(X, Y)}\}$. Moreover, there is an binary open set $(P, Q)_{(X, Y)}$ containing (x, y) such that $(P, Q)_{(X, Y)} \subseteq \bigcap \{(S, T)_i | i \in I_{(X, Y)}\}$ and $(P, Q)_{(X, Y)} \cap ((P, Q) \setminus \bigcup \{(U, V)_i | i \in I - I_{(X, Y)}\}) = (\phi, \phi)$.

If $(P, Q) = \bigcup \{(P, Q)_{(x, y)} | (x, y) \in (A, B)\}$ then clearly $(A, B) \subseteq (P, Q) \cap b-cl(A, B)$. Let $(k, l) \in (P, Q) \cap b-cl(A, B)$. Then $(k, l) \in (P, Q)_{(x, y)}$ for some $(x, y) \in (A, B)$. Since $(k, l) \in b-cl(A, B) = \bigcup \{b-cl((A, B) \cap (U, V)_i) | i \in I\}$ we have $(k, l) \in b-cl((A, B) \cap (U, V)_j)$ for some $j \in I$. Hence $j \in I_{(X, Y)}$ and $(P, Q)_{(X, Y)} \subseteq (S, T)_j$. Thus $(k, l) \in (S, T)_j \cap b-cl((A, B) \cap (U, V)_j) = (A, B) \cap (U, V)_j \subseteq (A, B)$. It follows that $(A, B) = (P, Q) \cap b-cl(A, B)$.

Theorem 2.2. *For a binary T_1 -space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) the following are equivalent:*

1. $(A, B) \in BLC(X, Y)$ if and only if $(X, Y) - (A, B) \in BLC(X, Y)$.
2. $BLC(X, Y)$ is binary closed under finite unions.
3. The boundary of each binary open set is a discrete subset.
4. The boundary of each binary semi-open set is a discrete subset.
5. Every binary semi-open set is binary locally closed.

Proof. (1) \Leftrightarrow (2) is obvious.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) : Let (P, Q) be binary open and let $(x, y) \in bd(P, Q) \cap b-cl(P, Q) \cap ((X, Y) - (P, Q))$. By assumption, if $(A, B) = (P, Q) \cup \{(x, y)\}$ then $(A, B) \in BLC(X, Y)$. Let $(A, B) = (S, T) \cap b-cl(A, B)$ for some binary open set (S, T) . One easily verifies that $(S, T) \cap bd(P, Q) = \{(x, y)\}$.

(3) \Rightarrow (4) : Let (A, B) be binary semi-open in (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) and let $(P, Q) = b-int(A, B)$. Then $bd(A, B) \subseteq bd(P, Q)$ and hence $bd(A, B)$ is a discrete subset.

(4) \Rightarrow (5) : Let (A, B) be binary semi-open in (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) . For each $(x, y) \in (A, B) \cap bd(A, B)$ there is an binary open set (P, Q) such that $(P, Q)_{(X, Y)} \cap bd(A, B) = \{(x, y)\}$. If $(P, Q) = b-int(A, B) \cup [\cup\{(P, Q)_{(X, Y)} | (x, y) \in (A, B) \cap bd(A, B)\}]$ it is easily verified that $(A, B) = (P, Q) \cap b-cl(A, B)$.

(5) \Rightarrow (1) : We will show that any union of an binary open set and a binary closed set is binary locally closed. Let $(C, D) = (E, F) \cup (G, H)$ where (E, F) is binary open and (G, H) is binary closed. We may assume that $(E, F) \cap (G, H) = (\phi, \phi)$. If $(A, B) = (E, F) \cup b-cl(E, F) \cap (G, H)$ then (A, B) is binary semi-open and hence $(A, B) = (S, T) \cap b-cl(A, B) = (S, T) \cap b-cl(A, B) = (S, T) \cap cl(E, F)$ for some binary open set (S, T) . If $(W, Z) = (S, T) \cup ((X, Y) - b-cl(E, F))$ then clearly $(C, D) = (W, Z) \cap b-cl(C, D)$. Thus $(C, D) \in BLC(X, Y)$.

3. Binary g -Locally Closed Sets

Definition 3.1. A subset (A, B) of a binary topological space (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) , is called

1. binary Generalized locally closed set (briefly $bglc$) if $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap (G, H)$, where (E, F) is binary g -open and (G, H) is binary g -closed in (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) .
2. $bg-lc^*$ -set if $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap (G, H)$, where (E, F) is binary g -open set and (G, H) is binary closed set in (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) .
3. $bg-lc^{**}$ -set if $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap (G, H)$, where (E, F) is binary open set and (G, H) is binary g -closed set in (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) .

The collection of all binary Generalized locally closed sets (resp. $bg-lc^*$ -sets and $bg-lc^{**}$ -sets) of (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) will be denoted by $BGLC(X, Y)$ (resp. $BGLC^*(X, Y)$ and $BGLC^{**}(X, Y)$).

Remark 3.1. Every binary g -closed set (resp. binary g -open set) is $bglc$.

Theorem 3.1. For a subset (A, B) of (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) , the following are equivalent.

1. $(A, B) \in BGLC^*(X, Y)$.
2. $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap b-cl(A, B)$ for some binary g -open set (E, F) .
3. $b-cl(A, B) - (A, B)$ is binary g -closed.
4. $(A, B) \cup ((P, Q) - b-cl(A, B))$ is binary g -open.

Proof. (1) \Rightarrow (2) Let $(A, B) \in BGLC^*(X, Y)$. Then $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap (G, H)$ where (E, F) is binary g -open and (G, H) is binary closed. Since $(A, B) \subseteq (E, F)$ and $(A, B) \subseteq b-cl(A, B)$, $(A, B) \subseteq (E, F) \cap b-cl(A, B)$. Conversely, since $(A, B) \subseteq (G, H)$, $b-cl(A, B) \subseteq (G, H)$, we have $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap (G, H)$ contains $(E, F) \cap b-cl(A, B)$. That is $(E, F) \cap b-cl(A, B) \subseteq (A, B)$. Therefore we have $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap b-cl(A, B)$.

(2) \Rightarrow (1) Since (E, F) is binary g -open and $b-cl(A, B)$ is binary closed, $(E, F) \cap b-cl(A, B) \in BGLC^*(X, Y)$ by Definition of $BGLC^*(X, Y)$.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap b-cl(A, B)$ implies that $b-cl(A, B) - (A, B) = b-cl(A, B) \cap (E, F)^c$ which is binary g -closed, Since $(E, F)^c$ is binary g -closed.

(3) \Rightarrow (2) Let $(E, F) = (b-cl(A, B) - (A, B))^c$. Then by assumption, (E, F) is binary g -open in (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) and $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap b-cl(A, B)$.

(3) \Rightarrow (4) $(A, B) \cup ((P, Q) - b-cl(A, B)) = (A, B) \cup (b-cl(A, B))^c = (b-cl(A, B) - (A, B))^c$ and by assumption $(b-cl(A, B) - (A, B))^c$ is binary g -open and $(A, B) \cup ((P, Q) - b-cl(A, B))$ is binary g -open.

(4) \Rightarrow (3) Let $(E, F) = (A, B) \cup (b-cl(A, B))^c$. Then $(E, F)^c$ is binary g -closed and $(E, F)^c = b-cl(A, B) - (A, B)$ and therefore $b-cl(A, B) - (A, B)$ is binary g -closed.

Theorem 3.2. *For a subset (A, B) of (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) , the following statements are equivalent.*

1. $(A, B) \in BGLC(X, Y)$.
2. $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap b-gcl(A, B)$ for some binary g -open set (E, F) .
3. $b-gcl(A, B) - (A, B)$ is binary g -closed.
4. $(A, B) \cup (b-gcl(A, B))^c$ is binary g -open.
5. $(A, B) \subseteq b-gint((A, B) \cup (b-gcl(A, B))^c)$

Proof. (1) \Rightarrow (2) Let $(A, B) \in BGLC(X, Y)$. Then $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap (G, H)$, where (E, F) is binary g -open and (G, H) is binary g -closed. Since $(A, B) \subseteq (G, H)$, $b-gcl(A, B) \subseteq (G, H)$ and therefore $(E, F) \cap b-gcl(A, B) \subseteq (A, B)$. Also $(A, B) \subseteq (E, F)$ and $(A, B) \subseteq b-gcl(A, B)$ implies $(A, B) \subseteq (E, F) \cap b-gcl(A, B)$ and therefore $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap b-gcl(A, B)$.

(2) \Rightarrow (3) $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap b-gcl(A, B)$ implies $b-gcl(A, B) - (A, B) = b-gcl(A, B) \cap (E, F)^c$ which is binary g -closed since $(E, F)^c$ is binary g -closed.

(3) \Rightarrow (4) $A \cup (Ngcl(A))^c = (Ngcl(A) - A)^c$ and by assumption $(Ngcl(A) - A)^c$ is Ng -open and so is $A \cup (Ngcl(A))^c$.

(4) \Rightarrow (5) By assumption, $(A, B) \cup (b-gcl(A, B))^c = b-gint((A, B) \cup (b-gcl(A, B))^c)$ and hence $(A, B) \subseteq b-gint((A, B) \cup (b-gcl(A, B))^c)$.

(5) \Rightarrow (1) By assumption and since $(A, B) \subseteq b-gcl(A, B)$, $(A, B) = b-gint((A, B) \cup (b-gcl(A, B))^c) \cap b-gcl(A, B) \in BGLC(X, Y)$.

Theorem 3.3. *Let (A, B) be a subset of (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) . Then $(A, B) \in BGLC^{**}(X, Y)$ if and only if $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap b-gcl(A, B)$ for some binary open set (E, F) .*

Proof. Let $(A, B) \in BGLC^{**}(X, Y)$. Then $(P, Q) = (E, F) \cap (G, H)$ where (E, F) is binary open and (G, H) is binary g -closed. Since $(P, Q) \subseteq (G, H)$, $b-gcl(A, B) \subseteq (G, H)$. Now $(A, B) = (A, B) \cap b-gcl(A, B) = (E, F) \cap (G, H) \cap b-gcl(A, B) = (E, F) \cap b-gcl(A, B)$. Here the converse part is trivial.

Corollary 3.1. *Let (A, B) be a subset of (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) . If $(A, B) \in BGLC^{**}(X, Y)$, then $b-gcl(A, B) - (A, B)$ is binary g -closed and $(A, B) \cup (b-gcl(A, B))^c$ is binary g -open.*

Proof. Let $(A, B) \in BGLC^{**}(X, Y)$. Then by Theorem 3.3, $(A, B) = (E, F) \cap b-gcl(A, B)$ for some binary open set (E, F) and $b-gcl(A, B) - (A, B) = b-gcl(A, B) \cap (E, F)^c$ is binary g -closed in (X, Y, \mathcal{M}) . If $(G, H) = b-gcl(A, B) - (A, B)$, then $(G, H)^c = (A, B) \cup (b-gcl(A, B))^c$ and $(G, H)^c$ is binary g -open and therefore $(A, B) \cup (b-gcl(A, B))^c$ is binary g -open.

References

- [1] O. Nethaji, R. Asokan and I. Rajasekaran, Novel concept of ideal nanotopological spaces, *Asia Mathematika*, 3(3)(2019), 5-15.
- [2] Carlos Granados, On binary α -open sets and binary α - ω -open sets in binary topological spaces, *South Asian Journal of Mathematics*, 11(1)(2021), 1-11.
- [3] S.Jayalakshmi and A.Manonmani, Binary regular beta closed sets and binary regular beta open sets in binary topological spaces, *The International Journal of Analytical and Experimental Modal Analysis*, Vol 12(4)(2020), 494-497.
- [4] N. Levine, Generalized closed sets in topology, *Rent. Circ. Mat. Palermo*, 19(2)(1970), 89-96.
- [5] H. Maki, R. Devi, and K. Balachandran, Generalized α -closed sets in topology, *Bull. Fukuoka Univ, Ed., Part (III)(42)(1993)*, 13-21.
- [6] H. Maki, R. Devi, and K. Balachandran, Associate topologies of generalized α -closed sets and α -generalized closed sets, *Mem. Fac. Kochi Univ. Ser. A. Math.*, (15)(1994), 51-63.
- [7] A. S. Mashhour, M. E. Abd El-Monsef, and S. N. EL-Deeb, α -Open mappings, *Acta. Math. Hungar.*, (41)(1983), 213-218.
- [8] S. Nithyanantha Jothi and P.Thangavelu, Topology between two sets, *Journal of Mathematical Sciences & Computer Applications*, 1(3)(2011), 95-107.
- [9] S. Nithyanantha Jothi and P. Thangavelu, Generalized binary closed sets in binary topological spaces, *Ultra Scientist Vol.26(1)(A)(2014)*, 25-30.
- [10] S. Nithyanantha Jothi, Binary semi open sets in binary topological spaces, *International Journal of Mathematical Archieve*, 7(9)(2016), 73-76.
- [11] O. Njastad, On some classes of nearly open sets, *Pacific. J. Math.*, (15)(1965), 961-970.
- [12] I. Rajasekaran and O. Nethaji, An introductory notes to ideal binanotopological spaces, *Asia Mathematika*, 3(1)(2019), 47-59.
- [13] I. Rajasekaran and O. Nethaji, Unified approach of several sets in ideal nanotopological spaces, *Asia Mathematika*, 3(1)(2019), 70-78.